

An Analysis on the Effect of Mobility and Load on Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework for Pervasive Environments

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Abstract

Service Selection in Pervasive environments is a challenging research domain as it enables the user to identify the best service provider based on its requirements. Fault tolerant Service selection framework protects the pervasive environment from various faults thereby providing seamless service to the users. However, the effect of mobility of the service providers, users on the performance of the framework and the effect of load on the performance of the system is challenging and unexplored. Therefore in this paper, an attempt has been made to simulate a pervasive environment and analyze the effect of mobility and load on the Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework. The experimental results show that mobility and load affects the performance of the system.

Keywords: Pervasive Environment, Fault Tolerance, Service Selection, Multi Criteria Decision Making, PROMETHEE, Load, Mobility.

1. Introduction

Pervasive Computing is a challenging area of research where the devices that provide various services are embedded in the environments. Pervasive environments consist of many service providers which are capable of providing services to users based on their requirements. The service providers and users move randomly in the pervasive environments and the service providers will have the capability to handle different loads in the environments. Pervasive environments are prone to faults. Shiva Chetan, Anand Ranganathan and Campbell, R. (2005) classified the faults that occur in the pervasive system as service failures, device failures, network failures and application failures. These faults greatly interrupt the service execution. The Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework provides service with minimal service delay even when there are faults in the pervasive environments. Many researchers have

proposed Fault Tolerant Service Selection methodologies to provide seamless service to the users. Even though the methodologies for fault tolerant system were proposed, the effect of mobility and the load on the performance of the system has not been explored. Therefore in this paper, efforts have been taken to create pervasive environment and simulate the Service Selection Framework which is Fault Tolerant and the effect of mobility and load on the performance has been analyzed.

The related work has been discussed in section 2. The fault tolerant service selection framework has been dealt in section 3. Experiments were conducted and the results were obtained and have been discussed in Section 4. Finally, the section 5 concludes.

2. Related Work

In recent years, researchers have focused on proposing fault tolerant mechanisms to provide seamless services in pervasive environment. Some of the relevant fault tolerant schemes are discussed in this section.

Shameem Ahmed, Sheikh I. Ahamed, Moushumi Sharmin and Chowdhury S. Hasan (2009) proposed fault healing methodology that stored all the crucial information including log status of the faulty device when the device fell into trouble. The healing manager (Shameem Ahmed, Moushumi Sharmin and Sheikh I. Ahamed, 2005) re-collected all information so that the device could restore its previous condition. Information Distribution process distributed the important information among other existing devices to assist a faulty device for keeping all the important information safe and secured. The main drawback is that the system requires user intervention if the selection of the service was based on the user's preferences.

Moushumi Sharmin, Shameem Ahmed, and Sheikh I. Ahamed (2005) proposed a SAFE- RD discovery mechanism as an integral part of MARKS. The resource manager component facilitated resource look up and efficient information dissemination. Peizhao Hu, Jadwiga Indulska and Ricky Robinson (2008) proposed a model-based autonomic context management system that dynamically configured and reconfigured its context information by gathering and preprocessing functionality, which provided fault tolerant provisioning of context information. The fault healing approach discussed the fault that could occur in the environment where sensors are placed. It had not considered about other failures such as communication failures and faults that occur in the processing system.

Amir Padovitz, Seng W. Loke and Arkady Zaslavsky (2008) proposed an ECORA framework for context-aware computing reasoned about context under uncertainty. The framework followed an agent-oriented hybrid approach, combining centralized reasoning services with context-aware, reasoning capable mobile software agents. It considered only the uncertainty that occur in the context. Weigang Wu, Jiannong Cao and Jin Yanga (2008) proposed a permission-based message efficient mutual exclusion (MUTEX) algorithm for mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs).

Koushanfar, F., Potkonjak, M. and Sangiovanni-Vincentelli, A (2002) proposed heterogeneous back-up scheme that addressed the problem of embedded sensor network fault tolerance, where one type of resources was substituted with another. The heterogeneous back up scheme provided a low cost, low overhead, high resilient fault tolerant technique but it have not considered about the application that was under execution.

Galizia S., Gugliotta A., and Domingue J, (2007) attempted to enhance the capability-driven selection in semantic web service frameworks using trust based selection criteria. Galizia S., Gugliotta A., and Domingue J, (2007) presented a Web Services Trust Ontology which enabled the users to describe semantically their trust requirements and guarantees. The emphasis was on trust and not on any other QoS parameters. Trust need not be the only QoS factor that requires to be considered; there can also be other factors such as cost, availability, reliability etc. (Gao Zhi-peng, Chen Jian, QIU Xue-song and MENG Luo-ming, (2009), Haibin Cai, Xiaohui Hu, Qingchong Lu and Qiying Cao (2009), Hei-Chia Wang, Chang-Shing Lee and Tsung-Hsien Ho (2007), Kim M.J., Kumar M. and Shirazi B.A (2006)) that requires to be considered for service selection.

Themistoklis Bourdenas, Morris Sloman and Emil C. Lupu (2010) proposed a Starfish based self-healing framework that followed the Self-Managed Cell architectural paradigm. Starfish was an instantiation of an SMC for wireless sensor networks. The framework defined the faults that could be found on sensors and respective handling services. High fault-detection accuracy was maintained with implicit redundancy of sensors avoiding dense deployment of sensing devices that observed the same attribute. Starfish based self healing framework was based on defined faults alone.

In the next section, the Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework has been discussed in detail.

3. Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework

The Pervasive Environment can be clustered based on geographical regions. Each geographical region has a set of service providers. In general

$$G_n = \{P_{n1}, P_{n2}, P_{n3}, \dots, P_{nm}\}$$

where n is the number of geographical regions and m is the number of service providers in a particular geographical region. If there are four geographical regions G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4 in a pervasive environment, and if the Service providers P_{11}, P_{12}, P_{13} and Users $U_{11}, U_{12}, U_{13}, U_{14}$ are available in a particular geographical region G_1 . Then,

$$G_1 = \{P_{11}, P_{12}, P_{13}, U_{11}, U_{12}, U_{13}, U_{14}\}$$

$$G_n = \{P_{n1}, P_{n2}, P_{n3}, \dots, P_{nm}, U_{n1}, U_{n2}, \dots, U_{nl}\}$$

Let each service provider provide a set of services such as

$$P_{11} = \{s_{111}, s_{112}, s_{113}\}$$

$$P_{12} = \{s_{121}, s_{122}, s_{123}\}$$

Figure 1: Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework

The Fault Tolerant Service Selection Framework has been shown in Fig. 1. The Framework consists of Service Registration Unit, User Registration Unit, Service Selection Unit, Service Delivery Unit and Monitoring unit. Each Service provider furnishes the services it wishes to provide and

registers it with the service registration unit. The user registration unit facilitates willing users who are interested in availing services to register.

The service selection unit helps in identifying the required service provider based on the users requirements. It selects the best service through PROMETHEE methodology (Salaja Silas et al (2011), Gul Ozerol and Esra Karasakal, (2008), Li Wei-xiang and Li Bang-yi, (2010), Majid Behzadian et al, (2010), Roux O., et al, (2008)) and provides to the user. This methodology provides the users to select the criteria of their own interest based on their requirement and also to give preferences to those criteria in terms of weights.

The information from the user provides the weighted user's preference for each criteria Cr , termed as weights $\{w_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, k\}$ that are normalized to 1. The information from the service providers is the set of relevant services that have similar functionality to form n_{fs} feasible service providers. The preference function of the service providers is calculated for maximization criterion as well as the minimization criterion.

The Qualitative Preference function is defined as 1 if the difference between the criteria of two service providers is greater than zero or otherwise defined as 0. The pair wise comparisons of various criteria are performed from the feasible set of service providers and the aggregated preference indices are defined. Let $s_x, s_y \in S$, where S is a set of service providers offering a particular service, then the Aggregated Preference Indices is given by

$$\begin{cases} \pi(s_x, s_y) = \sum_{j=1}^k P_j(s_x, s_y)w_j \\ \pi(s_y, s_x) = \sum_{j=1}^k P_j(s_y, s_x)w_j \end{cases}$$

$\pi(sp_x, sp_y)$ expresses the degree in which the service provider s_x preferred over the service provider s_y over all the criteria and $\pi(s_y, s_x)$ expresses the degree in which the service provider s_y is preferred over service provider s_x . The net outranking flow for each service provider s_a is calculated using

$$\phi(s_a) = \frac{1}{n_{fs} - 1} \left(\sum_{x \in S} \pi(s_a, s_x) - \sum_{x \in S} \pi(s_x, s_a) \right)$$

Where n_{fs} is the number of service providers that provide identical functionality. The service selection unit selects the service provider with the highest net outranking flow as the best service provider.

Fault handling unit monitors the services of the service provider and initiates corrective measures whenever there is a fault thereby providing fault tolerance to the framework. It keeps track of all the services that are allotted to the registered users' and monitors whether the execution of the allotted service has been completed successfully.

4. Implementation Results

A pervasive environment was generated. The service providers were permitted to register initially for providing services to the users. The users who are interested in availing the services were also permitted to register. The fault tolerant service selection framework was implemented and the simulation results were obtained.

Experiment 4.1

Each service provider was permitted to offer services. The number of Service providers was set as 30. The mobility was set as 40 m/sec. Faults were generated in the environment such that 30% of the service provider is at fault. The maximum load on the service provider was varied as 20 %, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% and the effect of load on the fault tolerant behavior was studied and is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Effect of load on the Fault Tolerant behavior

It was found that as load on the service provider is increased, the success rate is reduced and the performance of the system is affected. This is due to the fact that at a particular time t, when a fault occurs at the pervasive environment whose service providers have lighter load, the framework will be able to successfully identify the next best service provider and the service requests are successfully completed. However, when a fault occurs during a state where service providers are heavily loaded, the framework even though identifies the next best service provider but due to its heavy load it cannot accept the new service requests and the success rate is affected. Therefore for a particular time t, the success rate is higher for lighter load and lower for higher load and it follows a polynomial function

$$y = ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + k \tag{4.1}$$

Table 1: Values of eqn. 4.1

S.No	Load %	a	b	c	d	k
1.	20	-1.3125	18.958	-96.562	220.6	-141.5
2.	40	-1.3542	20.19	-105.08	237.09	-150.83
3.	60	-1.2542	18.964	-99.204	222.29	-140.5
4.	80	-0.8542	13.819	-76.687	181.5	-117.5
5.	100	-0.8333	13.204	-72.056	168.19	-108.33

Experiment 4.2

During the operation of the pervasive environment, the number of Service providers was set as 30. Each service provider was permitted to offer services. The maximum load on the service provider was set as 40 % and the service providers were set to move randomly. The mobility of the service provider was varied as 20 m/s, 40 m/s, 60 m/s, 80m/s and the effect of mobility on the Fault tolerance behavior was studied and is shown in Fig. 3

Figure 3: Effect of mobility on the success rate

It is found that as the mobility of the service provider increases the success rate decreases. This is due to the fact that when the service provider and user is less mobile, the probability of the service provider/ user moving into a different geographical region is less and therefore the performance is good. It is observed that for lesser mobility, the success rate follows the logarithmic function,

$$y = a \ln(x) + c \tag{4.2}$$

Table 2: Values for eqn. 4.2

S.No	Mobility m/sec	a	c
1	20	61.646	-0.2257
2	40	57.024	1.1378
3	60	51.754	1.5828

However, when a service provider/ user is highly mobile, the probability of the service provider/ user moving into a different geographical region is higher and therefore the success rate is relatively lower at a particular time t. Therefore higher the mobility of the service provider the success rate is affected. It is observed that for higher mobility, the success rate follows the polynomial function,

$$y = ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + k \tag{4.3}$$

Table 3: Values for eqn. 4.3

S.No	Mobility m/sec	A	b	c	d	k
1.	80	-0.7083	11.25	-63.292	158.75	106
2.	100	-0.7292	11.106	-59.951	143.78	-93.833

Experiment 4.3

During the operation of the pervasive environment, the number of Service providers was set as 30. Each service provider was permitted to offer services. The maximum load on the service provider was set as 40 %. Mobility was set as 40 m/sec. The load on the service provider is varied as 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%. Faults were generated in the environment such that 30 % of the service provider is at fault. The effect of service recovery overhead for different loads on the service provider was obtained and is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Effect of load on Service Recovery overhead

It was observed that the load on the service provider affects the service recovery head. For higher load, the service recovery overhead is relatively higher. It is observed it follows a linear function

$$y = mx + k \quad (4.4)$$

Table 4: Values for eqn. 4.4

S.No	Load %	m	k
1	20	5	-5
2	40	4	-4
3	60	3	-3
4	80	2	-2
5	100	1	-1

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the effect of mobility and load on the service provider for Service selection framework for Pervasive environments was studied by conducting adequate experiments. It was found that as load on the service provider is increased, the success rate is reduced and the performance of the system is affected. The experimental results show that higher the mobility of the service provider the success rate is affected. It was also observed that the load on the service provider affects the service recovery head. For higher load, the service recovery overhead is relatively higher.

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